

SOCIAL MEDIA & ACADEMIC PERFORMANCES: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Internet is a great boon in our life. It helps in every aspect s of life. It is a very large community which is using internet for pure education, but unfortunately we have also a large number of people including majority of youth & teenager using internet for social network such as Orkut, Facebook, Twitter Myspace etc. Social media/ Social Networking is one of the Technological foundation of Web 2.0 which allow people to create, share, exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and network's. It is the social interaction among people in which they can create share or exchange information.

Introduction

Internet is a great boon in our life. It helps in every aspect s of life. It is a very large community which is using internet for pure education, but unfortunately we have also a large number of people including majority of youth & teenager using internet for social network such as Orkut, Facebook, Twitter Myspace etc. Social media/ Social Networking is one of the Technological foundation of Web 2.0 which allow people to create, share, exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and network s. It is the social interaction among people in which they can create share or exchange information.

Furthermore Social Media depends on mobile and web-based technologies to create highly interactive platforms through which individuals and share, co-create, discuss user generated content. In the year 2003, a new social networking sites Facebook & Orkut.com change total concept of Social Network in the history of Social media. Social Networking such as Facebook, Orkut, Myspace, Flickr and Youtube are sites where users apply for membership and maintain their personal profile information in a centrally organized database .Each network member controls access to their profile by accepting or deleting request from other network members to be "friend ".

By expanding and developing their networks of friend s, social networking members are able to maintain online relationship for work, study, special interests leisure- related purposes. Platform like Twitter, Facebook, and Myspace have created online communities, where people can share as much or as little personal information as they desire with other members. The result is an enormous amount of information that can be easily shared, searched, promoted, disputed and created. Social Networking services utilize the participation technology and software tools such as blogs, wikis instant messaging, chat room message boards and social bookmarking to share online ideas, videos,

photos etc. Put simply, social networking is a way for one person to meet up with other people on the Internet. People use social networking sites for meeting new friends, finding old friends, or locating people who have the same problems or interests they have, called niche networking. Social Networking Sites are the example of techno-oriented communication.

Facebook, Friendster, Twitter, Yahoo Messenger, and Skype are examples of the new phenomenon of online social networking. It is through these sites that people come in contact of their society members to seek mates, search for entertainment and participate in political spheres. It wasn't the founders of Facebook, or Twitter, or even My Space or Friendster. Social media - the exchange of media within networks of friends and acquaintances is much older than the Internet.

Review of Literature

Aasha Vanve1 et al., (2016) web usage presents a wholly new learning atmosphere for college kids, so requiring a distinct talent set to achieve success. Important thinking, research, and analysis skills square measure growing in importance as students have increasing volumes of data from a spread of sources to kind through. Also, notably in courses that square measure entirely electronic, student's square measure far more freelance than within the ancient setting. This needs that they be extremely actuated and committed to learning, with less social interaction with peers or a coach. Students in on-line courses tend to try and do furthermore as those in lecture rooms, however there's higher incidence of withdrawal or incomplete grades. E-learning is viewed as laptop motor-assisted learning and as pedagogy for student targeted and cooperative learning. Early developments in e learning centered on laptop motor-assisted learning, wherever half or all of the training content is delivered digitally. a lot of recently the education dimension of web usage has become outstanding. Web usage includes all

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styles of electronically supported learning and teaching.

Ben Akko, (2011) data and communication technologies have created vital contributions to our social, economic, and political structures. It's conjointly contributed to education. Basification, group action, access, and constraints of distance in education are addressed victimization the web to foster interactions and collaboration among learners and instructors, associated to deliver content in a more and more globalized world. In recent times, social media has entered the fray that although empowering, is additionally disenfranchising - a duality that's typically perceived from its unquiet tendencies than from its sanctioning attributes, generally to socio-political structures however specifically to education.

This study argues that the expansion of the web is very important for teaching and learning in this it facilitates education in ways in which were antecedently difficult. It acknowledges the expansion of social media as associate rising web technology which will add price and profit existing ways of on-line or distance education if they're consistently and homogeneously applied. It explores the adult learning context, examines the characteristics of adult learning, describes social media and its affordances, aligns adult learning characteristics to social media affordance, explores, through the employment of a framework, commonalities between adult learning characteristics and social media affordance, and from this hypothesize that social media is effective in teaching and learning. This study has implications on pedagogy and on content delivery within the post-secondary level.

Adrian Kirkwood, (2014) The term Technology-enhanced learning (TEL) is employed to explain the applying of data and communication technologies to teaching and learning. Express statements concerning what the term is known to mean square measure rare associated it's not evident that a shared understanding has been developed in pedagogy of what constitutes an improvement of the scholar learning expertise. This study presents a review and assessment of however TEL is understood in recent literature. It examines the aim of technology interventions, the approaches adopted to demonstrate the role of technology in enhancing the training expertise, differing ways that within which improvement is formed and also the use of assorted forms proof to substantiate claims concerning TEL. Thematic analysis enabled classes to be developed and relationships explored between the aims of TEL

interventions, the proof given, and also the ways that within which improvement is formed.

Jasmine An sari et al., (2012) The rising trends of hybrid web usage and internet a pair of.0 technologies square measure a byproduct of the unexampled advancements of data technology. Understanding and experimenting on however technology fits into the advanced realities of lecture rooms has resulted in vital shifts in learning trends towards a lot of internet primarily based atmosphere as opposition the previous general teacher-student atmosphere. The education sector in Asian country has seen huge progress within the past decades with specific efforts place into educating the feminine population to empower girls. Blue blood prophet Bin king University (PMU), a new established not-for-profit university accredited by the Ministry of upper Education, having a field specifically dedicated to feminine students has been chosen for case study. This analysis is an endeavor to know the advantages and challenges of implementing hybrid web usage and internet a pair of.0 application primarily based atmosphere to teach feminine students. Results of the investigation prove that introducing such learning environments will have vital impacts on improvement of students' analysis method, analysis capabilities, and communication skills. Finally, we have a tendency to show however this technology also can yield similar in leads to alternative countries and alternative institutes.

The Nature of Social Networking Sites and Low Academic Performances

Social networking sites as web-based services that allow individuals to: (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system.

For the past years, social networking has been very popular for people worldwide. Social networking is a great form of entertainment. It is like going to a new school, on your first day you have no friends but as days pass you will meet new friends and eventually you will form groups or circle of friends. At first, you don't have much interest in your new school but when you begin to learn and enjoy more about your school, you will be happy to spend much of your time in school with your friends, teachers and etc. It is open for all kinds of people, all ages, and all races. A purpose of social networking is we meet people, maybe people we met before like old classmates or schoolmate or new people from different races and countries, we just have same interests with.

For teens in this generation, social networking has become sort of an “addiction”. A teenager has a Facebook account. She opens her account daily to check new updates. She spends hours checking new updates until she realizes she has more important things to do like school works she has missed doing because of signing in into a social network service. This is an example of a teen being addicted to such social networks. To prove social networking can be an addiction, the researchers made a survey to test whether social networking could be a hindrance to a good performance in school. The survey made got answers that yes, some people are willing to spend more time being online on these social network services than to spend time studying and working up on school works. This is sad to hear because with all the advantages social networking can give, there are also disadvantages, like this, that can be or give bad effects to people who use them.

Conclusion

The social media engages students and have to be examined as entrepreneurs of understanding. The medium of internet is marketing with increase in its programs. The interactive character of online conditions has extended with social networking. Hooking up through social networking began as being a niche activity, though time it's a phenomenon. The web sites are employed in many ways like developing metropolitan areas, speaking, blogging etc. Additionally, different institutions even nowadays are developing groups on several Websites.

The improved usage of Websites has become a worldwide phenomenon for quite some time. What began out as being a hobby for several computer literate people has converted to a social norm and existence-style for individuals from around the globe. Teens and teenagers have especially recognized these internet sites to be able to contact their peers, share information, reinvent their personas, and showcase their social lives.

While using the increase of technology helpful for getting together with others along with the recognition on the internet, Internet sites are now being an activity that's done mainly on the web, with Websites.

According to Facebook users often time experience poor performance academically. Similarly, posit that social media is negatively associated with academic performance of student and is a lot more momentous than its advantages. Internet addiction consequently gave rise in internet usage within the last couple of decades. Recommended that addicted users prefer using internet setting back their

personal and professional responsibilities which ultimately leads to poor academic performance. According to pointed out that Facebook users devoted lesser time to their studies in comparison to nonusers did and subsequently had lower GPAs. Also mentioned that among various unique distractions of every single generation, Facebook remains a major distraction of current generation.

References

1. Aasha Vanve1 et al., Influence of Parents“ Education on Achievement Motivation of Adolescents.Indian Journal of Social Science Researches, vol. 6, Issue 1,pp. 72-79, 2016.
2. Ben Akko, Motivational Variables and Academic Performance of Urban and Rural Secondary School Students in Nigeria. KEDI Journal of Education Policy, vol. 5, Issue 2, pp. 23- 39, 2011.
3. Adrian Kirkwood, Emotional Intelligence and Parental Involvement as Predictors of Students“ Achievement in Financial Accounting. American Journal of Social and Management Sciences, vol. 2, Issue 1, pp. 21-25, 2014.
4. Jasmine An sari et al., A Comparative Study of Effect of Parental Environment Upon the Educational Development of Students on the Basis of Sex. Indian Psychological Review, vol. 48, Issue 4, pp. 193-196, 2012.
5. Bob Fix et al., Approaches, Methods and Techniques in English Language. ELT Journal, vol. 4, Issue 5, pp. 6-12, 2016.
6. Agarwal, Nidhi; Kumar, Puneet (2009). “Reflection on the new Innovations for maximizing the learning in Teacher of Mathematics”, International Journal Educational Herald Vol. 38 No. 2 Pp. 41 ISSN: 0974-0732.
7. Pei subgenus Chen Sun, An Examination of Achievement, Motivation, Self- Regulation, confident and Methods of Entry. Higher Education Research and Development, vol. 18, Issue 1, pp. 31- 54, 2014.

